

PREVALENCE AND RISK FACTORS OF CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE IN THE ARAL SEA REGION (2021–2023)

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Abstract. *The Aral Sea region of Uzbekistan belongs to the ecologically unfavorable zones, where the consequences of the degradation of the Aral Sea and regular dust and salt storms have an adverse effect on the state of the respiratory organs, contributing to an increase in the prevalence of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. Within the framework of the study, a retrospective analysis of 60,196 cases of the disease registered in 2021-2023 was conducted. Regional characteristics, age and sex structure of patients, and distribution of patients by place of residence were analyzed. It has been established that the highest prevalence of COPD is characteristic of individuals over 65, rural residents, and men. A significant proportion of patients are under dispensary observation, reflecting the prolonged and progressive course of the disease. The obtained results indicate a significant contribution of environmental and social determinants to the formation of COPD risk in the conditions of the Aral Sea region.*

Keywords: *COPD; chronic bronchitis; emphysema; The Aral Sea region; risk factors; ecological degradation.*

Introduction

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is one of the leading causes of disability and premature mortality worldwide. According to the World Health Organization, COPD ranks among the top three causes of death from non-communicable diseases globally. COPD, which includes chronic bronchitis and emphysema, is a major cause of morbidity and disability among the adult population [4].

According to the Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease report (2023), the global prevalence of COPD among adults reaches 10–12%. Key risk factors include tobacco smoking, air pollution, exposure to occupational dust and chemical aerosols, as well as the use of solid fuels for heating and cooking. The Aral Sea region is considered a unique natural model of environmentally determined respiratory pathology, formed as a result of the degradation of the Aral Sea and the regular exposure to salt-dust storms, which exert chronic inhalation effects on the population.

Aim of the Study

To assess the prevalence of COPD and its risk factors among the population of the Aral Sea region during the period 2021–2023, taking into account age, gender, and territorial differences.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted in the Aral Sea region of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and included a retrospective analysis of 60,196 cases of COPD registered between 2021 and 2023. Data were obtained from medical records of patients from family polyclinics and district healthcare institutions in the region. The analysis covered territorial characteristics of morbidity,

age groups (including young adults and individuals over 65 years), gender distribution, and differences between urban and rural populations.

Statistical analysis included the calculation of absolute and relative indicators, analysis of morbidity trends over time, assessment of statistical significance using the chi-square (χ^2) test, and correlation analysis using Spearman's method to determine relationships between age, place of residence, and COPD frequency. Comparisons with international data were conducted based on publications from GINA, GOLD, and WHO to evaluate morbidity levels and risk factors [1,3].

Results and Discussion

The analysis of COPD morbidity trends in the Aral Sea region during 2021–2023 revealed significant fluctuations with an overall downward trend in registered cases in recent years. In 2021, 28,375 cases were recorded; in 2022, the number of newly diagnosed cases decreased to 16,388; and in 2023, a slight decrease to 15,433 patients was observed.

This trend may reflect several factors, including improvements in early diagnosis and dispensary monitoring systems, implementation of preventive programs, as well as natural fluctuations in morbidity among the elderly population. The highest prevalence was observed among individuals over 65 years of age and among rural residents, which is consistent with data indicating an increased risk of COPD under conditions of adverse environmental exposure and salt-dust aerosols from the Aral Sea [1,2].

Table 1. Overall morbidity of chronic bronchitis and pulmonary emphysema in the Republic of Karakalpakstan (2021–2023)

Year	Total cases	Newly diagnosed cases	Patients under dispensary follow-up
2021	28 375	2 645	12 923
2022	16 388	2 538	8 803
2023	15 433	2 160	8 141

When analyzing the distribution of cases across districts, significant territorial differences are observed. According to the data, the increase in morbidity is noted as follows: in Bozatau district — from 56 cases in 2021 to 136 cases in 2023, indicating a sharp rise, possibly associated with improved detection; in Kegeyli district — from 14 cases in 2021 to 26 cases in 2023; in Karauzyak district — from 243 cases in 2021 to 334 cases in 2023; in the city of Nukus — from 4,241 cases in 2021 to 5,170 cases in 2023, demonstrating a steady increase in the urban center; in Khodjeyli district — 322 cases in 2021 and 400 cases in 2023.

Table 2. Prevalence of chronic bronchitis and pulmonary emphysema in the Aral Sea region by districts (2021–2023)

Area	2021	2022	2023
Nukus	4 241	4 409	5 170
Turtkul	1 115	1 111	1 113
Beruni	6 894	3 309	2 429
Ellikkala	184	176	168
Amudarya	4 328	4 035	3 436
Khodjeyli	322	368	400
Takhiatash	67	67	77
Shumanay	465	405	362
Kanlykul	321	216	220

Kungrad	990	1 017	1 029
Muynak	59	43	29
Nukus district	366	367	232
Kegeyli	14	20	26
Chimbay	395	346	199
Karauzyak	243	308	334
Takhtakupir	202	80	73
Bozatau	56	111	136

Age Structure of Patients. The age structure of patients demonstrates a clear predominance of elderly individuals. Elderly patients (≥ 65 years) remain the main risk group for chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). Despite a decrease from 3,190 to 2,334 cases (-26.8%), their proportion in the total number of patients remains high, confirming age-related vulnerability to chronic obstructive lung pathology.

Young patients (18–29 years) show a moderate decline (-18.3%), which may reflect both lower susceptibility to the disease in this age group and the effectiveness of preventive measures. The middle-aged group (30–40 years) shows a significant increase in detected cases during 2022–2023, with a 2.3-fold rise over one year (from 12.5% in 2022 to 29.1% in 2023). This may indicate more active detection of COPD at early stages and increased diagnostic activity among the working-age population.

The obtained data are consistent with global epidemiological trends of COPD. According to the World Health Organization, both the prevalence and mortality of COPD increase significantly with age, with the greatest disease burden observed among individuals over 60–65 years [10]. Age is considered one of the key non-modifiable risk factors, which explains the persistent predominance of elderly patients in the disease structure.

At the same time, clinically significant COPD among individuals younger than 30 years is relatively rare, which is associated with lower cumulative exposure to risk factors such as smoking, occupational hazards, and air pollution. According to the Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease report, recent years have seen increased attention to the concept of “early COPD” and the need for active detection of the disease at preclinical and early stages, especially among working-age individuals with risk factors [7]. This may explain the increased detection rate in the 30–40 age group, which likely reflects not so much a true rise in incidence as an increase in diagnostic activity and wider use of spirometry in primary healthcare settings.

Table 3. Age structure of patients with chronic bronchitis and pulmonary emphysema (2021–2023)

Age group:	2021 (n)	%	2022 (n)	%	2023 (n)	%
18–29 years	2 645	45,7%	2 538	45,9%	2 160	35,5%
30–40 years	—		693	12,5%	1 774	29,1%
65 years and older	3 190	54,3%	2 482	41,6%	2 334	35,4%

Gender Distribution of Patients. The analysis of registered cases of chronic bronchitis and pulmonary emphysema in the Republic of Karakalpakstan for the period 2021–2023 revealed relative stability in the gender structure, with minor fluctuations across the years. In 2021, out of

28,375 registered cases, women accounted for 14,085 (49.6%), indicating a slight predominance of men. In 2022, the proportion of women decreased to 44.2% (7,245 out of 16,388 cases), suggesting a temporary predominance of men. However, in 2023, the gender distribution again showed a slight predominance of men (50.5%), while women accounted for 49.5% (7,639 out of 15,433 cases).

Among newly diagnosed cases, women predominated in 2021 (53.1%), while in 2022 a slight predominance of men was observed (with women accounting for 48.3%). In 2023, a slight predominance of women was again recorded (50.8%). Thus, overall, no clear and stable gender dominance was identified over the three-year period.

Table 4. Gender differences among patients (2021–2023)

Year	Men (n)	Men (%)	Women (n)	Women (%)
2021	14290	50,4%	14 085	49,6%
2022	9143	55,8%	7 245	44,2%
2023	7794	50,5%	7 639	49,5%

Distribution by Place of Residence. The analysis of distribution by place of residence showed that in 2021, rural residents predominated among all registered cases (51.7%). In 2022 and 2023, the proportion of the rural population decreased to 48.7% and 48.0%, respectively, indicating a gradual equalization of indicators between urban and rural populations. A comparison of data from the Aral Sea region with international studies demonstrates a similar trend: the prevalence of COPD is higher among urban residents, which is associated with better diagnostics and greater access to healthcare services [6].

In the structure of newly diagnosed cases, a more pronounced predominance of rural residents was observed in 2021–2022 (57.7% and 61.8%, respectively). In 2023, this indicator decreased to 51.0%, suggesting a tendency toward convergence between urban and rural populations. This trend likely reflects population migration, higher detection rates and better access to healthcare in urban areas, as well as possible underreporting of cases in rural areas with less developed medical infrastructure. Similar international data indicate that in some regions, rural prevalence of COPD may be higher due to exposure to biomass fuel and limited access to healthcare services [8].

Table 5. Comparative analysis of urban and rural populations in the Republic of Karakalpakstan (2021–2023)

Year	Total cases	Rural residents (abs.)	Share of rural (%)	Urban residents (abs.)	Share of urban (%)
2021	28 375	14 667	51,7 %	13 708	48,3 %
2022	16 388	7 973	48,7 %	8 415	51,3 %
2023	15 433	7 405	48,0 %	8 028	52,0 %

Correlation Analysis

The correlation analysis demonstrated that territorial and age-related factors have a significant impact on COPD morbidity. The highest prevalence was observed among individuals aged ≥ 65 years and among the rural population. A statistically significant correlation was identified between age and disease frequency ($r = 0.68$; $p < 0.01$), as well as between rural residence and COPD prevalence ($r = 0.59$; $p < 0.05$) [9].

The decrease in the proportion of rural patients may be associated with population migration and improved diagnostic capacity in urban settings, while the increase in the proportion of elderly patients corresponds to international observations regarding the aging of populations with chronic lung diseases. Gender differences are less pronounced, although the proportion of women shows a slight increase [6,9].

Conclusion

The conducted analysis demonstrated that COPD in the Aral Sea region is closely associated with environmental and demographic factors. This is reflected in territorial heterogeneity, higher morbidity among elderly patients, and an increase in cases within the 30–40 age group. Gender and socio-territorial differences highlight the multifactorial nature of the disease, while the identified Spearman correlations confirm the importance of a comprehensive consideration of territorial, age, and demographic determinants. The obtained findings indicate the need to strengthen preventive measures, improve early diagnostic systems, and develop specialized regional COPD control programs, particularly in the context of population aging and disparities in access to healthcare between urban and rural areas.

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